

NEANIAS

Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater and Space Challenges

Document: D10.5 NEANIAS open event

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NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the 'Prototyping New Innovative Services' challenge set out in the 'Roadmap for EOSC' foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community's research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighbouring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Abstract

The NEANIAS Open Event was planned for the last quarter of the project to present the objectives of the project, its motivations, the challenges undertaken, the results obtained and the innovative digital solutions available on the EOSC platform, offering a practical knowledge of NEANIAS from all perspectives (technological, functional, commercial, strategic), as well as the access to the project team. The event was aimed both to NEANIAS stakeholders and general audience. It was organized from the WP 10 “Communication, Dissemination and Outreach”, led by RICOH and had the support of the NEANIAS partners.

This document reports the **activities and results in the context of the organization of the NEANIAS Open Event**, carried on September 22nd and 23rd, 2022, in Sant Cugat del Vallès (Barcelona, Spain).

The document presents the work carried out considering throughout the process: the initial planning, including the strategic and organizational aspects, the details of the event developed, the results and impacts and finally a general description of the management and coordination model.

1. Introduction

NEANIAS is an ambitious project that comprehensively addresses the ‘Prototyping New Innovative Services’ challenge set out in the recent ‘Roadmap for EOSC’ foreseen actions. NEANIAS will drive the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. Each of these sectors considers a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies. Each thematic service will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. In doing so, NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community’s research and knowledge generation activities.

As stated above, one of the key tasks in the project is to communicate and disseminate the developments, outputs and benefits of NEANIAS to a wide spectrum of stakeholders in order to get their involvement and engagement, facilitating so the achievement of the objectives set. This task is developed taking into account different profiles, needs, interests, areas of application and each kind of relationship with the project.

As a key dissemination activity, an open event was planned for the last quarter of the project to present the objectives of the project, its motivations, the challenges undertaken, the results obtained and the innovative digital solutions available on the EOSC platform, offering a practical knowledge of NEANIAS from all perspectives (technological, functional, commercial, strategic), as well as the access to the project team. The event was aimed both to NEANIAS stakeholders and general audience.

This document reports the activities and results carried out in the context of the organization of the NEANIAS Open Event, carried on September 22 and 23, 2022, in Sant Cugat del Vallès (Barcelona, Spain).

It presents the work carried out considering its different stages: (i) the initial planification, including the strategic and organizational matters, (ii) all the details of the event developed, and finally (iii) the results and impacts. Finally, many illustrative pictures are provided in the annex to illustrate and record the NEANIAS Open Event held. All the personal information provided by third parties is presented considering the GDPR requirements.

2. Strategy and Planning

This section presents the work done in advance for the event definition and organization, considering the definition of objectives, the format, the date and place, the target analysis, the approach and the communication and engagement plan.

2.1. Objectives

A free open event to present the results of the NEANIAS project, exploit the potential of its novel technological solutions and interconnect innovation, business, and the public sector.

2.2. Format

The event consists of 3 sessions in 2 days, to be held both in person and online. The event language is English.

2.3. Date and Place

September 22-23, 2022. (online & Presential). The event took place at Esade Creapolis in Sant Cugat del Vallès (Barcelona, Spain).

2.3.1. About the Venue

Esade Creapolis is an Innovation Hub to connect talent, knowledge and organizations, by facilitating innovation, entrepreneurship and business development with social impact. It is located at Av. De la Torre Blanca, 57 · 08172 Sant Cugat del Vallés, Barcelona, Spain.

Fig. 1 Event venue

Next figure shows the location of the conference hall.

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Fig. 2 Event location

2.3.2. About the City

Sant Cugat del Vallès is a city located in the metropolitan area of Barcelona.

Fig. 3 Event city location

In 2022 Sant Cugat received the title of "City of Science and Innovation" from the Ministry of Science and Innovation of the state government. This recognition distinguishes the commitment of the city to promote Research, Development and Innovation (R+D+I) in the municipality as well as the support it gives to local companies with a strong scientific, technological and innovative component.

The Ministry evaluated different business, social and technological activities present in the city of the candidature from Sant Cugat. Likewise, it has also taken into account the City Council's innovative drive-in aspects of citizen attention, internal organization and procedural management. In particular, projects already underway have been evaluated such as the programme to promote innovative culture for municipal staff, the digital transformation of administrative processes, advice and attention to entrepreneurial companies, the creation of an innovation committee within the Office of Urban Agenda and municipal planning or sustainability projects financed through European funds.

Sant Cugat del Vallès is one of the ten municipalities that received the award this year in the category of municipalities between 20,000 and 100,000 inhabitants (Category B). With this award, Sant Cugat now becomes part of the Innpulso Network, a forum for meeting and defining innovative local policies where experiences and projects are shared. Currently, it is integrated by 83 cities throughout the state. The cities of the Innpulso Network also receive the support of the Ministry of Science and Innovation through the grants that are granted annually for the incorporation of local innovation agents in the municipal government structures, in order to strengthen the capacity to manage innovation policies at the local level.

2.4. Target

The event is aimed at researchers, scientists, entrepreneurs, innovators, companies, investors, business developers, consultants, disseminators, public managers, municipalities, and general public interested in Space, Underwater, Atmosphere science and novel Information Technologies.

The solutions are of specific interest for these areas and sectors of activity:

- Space: astrophysics, planetary scientists, planetary mining engineers, planetary robotics, mobile telecommunication and space weather in virtual observatories with a variety of visual discovery scenarios.
- Atmosphere: meteorologists, industrial air pollutant emitters, ecologists, rural urban planners and air quality authorities, geohazards, civil protection, insurance or health agencies.
- Underwater: Underwater surveys have numerous scientific and commercial applications in the fields of archaeology, geology, biology, and energy involving tasks such as ancient shipwreck prospection, ecological studies, environmental damage assessment, and detection of temporal changes.
- IT sector: Novel Information technologies, including Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Big Data, Cloud Computing, Visual Analytics, 3D Modelling, Image processing, Scientific visualization, High Performance Computing, Real time & Remote interaction.

2.5. Goals and approach

The event was planned to reach the widest audience possible, engaging all the potential profiles and fields. To this objective the content and structure presented from WP10 were discussed with the Project Management Board and all the partners. Finally, the following approach was agreed:

- Project results and the European Open Science Cloud: Session to find out everything about the project proposals, the challenges, the results obtained and all the opportunities in the European Open Science Cloud for business and research.
- Innovation and business: Session to participate in innovation and business workshops led by our innovation specialists and business consultants. Its goal is that attendees learn from the experiences of users already incorporated and discover more about their results and the benefits achieved.

- Technical session: Sessions to find out all about the innovative NEANIAS services available at EOSC from our experts and developers. Learn to make the most of its potential and apply it effectively to meet the needs of your projects or your research.
- Networking opportunities: Breaks, open questions and opportunities to meet and contact international experts, scientists and consultants in Space, Atmospheric and Submarine research, technical specialists in IT, investors and business developers, the European innovation ecosystem, and public policy managers.

2.6. Communication and engagement

A recurring activity of communication and engagement of the potential audience had to be carried out. This section summarizes the most relevant aspects.

2.6.1. Open Event identity

A visual identity for the open event was created to make it easily recognizable. This identity followed the guidelines already defined for the whole project.

Fig. 4 NEANIAS Open Event visual identity

The Open Event banner was present in all digital channels (social networks, website, zoom, newsletter, ...) and printed material (press releases, leaflets, media, ...), and was adapted according to any particular needs of the channel or the moment (for example, including calls to the subscription, or latest information).

2.6.2. Website and landing page

The open event banner was included on the NEANIAS home page, to promote it and make it easy for visitors to remember. A direct link to the open page has also been included in the main shortcuts in the content menu to make it easy to reach and be aware of the latest news.

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Fig. 5 NEANIAS website and Open Event (Home page)

The NEANIAS website was frequently updated with the latest news about the agenda, speakers, practical information, deadlines, and much more.

Fig. 6 NEANIAS website and Open Event (Event section)

2.6.3. Digital channels

To support the promotion of the event, its dissemination among the sectors and the general public, and attract the maximum number of attendees and participants, all NEANIAS digital

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channels were dedicated to achieving this common goal. Also, the different campaigns helped to promote the project itself, attracting visitors to the project website.

Twitter was very active in promoting the event, informing the audience with the content and the latest news (i.e., the agenda, the panelists, organizational issues, reminders, ...) and helping to promote interaction, networking and engagement from both the ecosystem (scientists, researchers, research infrastructures, thematic sectors, companies, EU organizations or related H2020 projects, among others) and the general public in an agile and effective way.

Fig. 7 NEANIAS Open Event on Twitter (sample)

Facebook facilitated the promotion of the event both to the general public and to the specific target, mainly through participation in discussion groups.

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Fig. 8 NEANIAS Open Event on Facebook (sample)

LinkedIn was focused on attracting professional public with an interest already identified in the project, achieving the endorsement by the ecosystem.

Fig. 9 NEANIAS Open Event on LinkedIn (sample)

Next figure illustrates the support on LinkedIn by the ecosystem.

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Fig. 10 NEANIAS Open Event on LinkedIn (sample)

YouTube introduced the NEANIAS event and services through video presentations about the project and many technical demonstrations. In addition, a dedicated playlist was created with some testimonials from the ecosystem.

Fig. 11 NEANIAS Open Event on YouTube (sample)

The NEANIAS newsletter made it possible to inform NEANIAS subscribers about the event, keeping them interested and attracting them to the event.

The NEANIAS Open Event will be soon, next Sept 22 and 23!

A free open event to present the results of the NEANIAS project, exploit the potential of its novel technological solutions and interconnect innovation, business, and the public sector. It will take place in Sant Cugat - Barcelona, on September 22 and 23, 2022.

Save the date!

The event is aimed at researchers, scientists, entrepreneurs, innovators, companies, investors, business developers, consultants, disseminators, public managers, and general public interested in Space, Underwater, Atmosphere and novel Information Technologies.

Find out everything at [NEANIAS Open Event](#).

All the registration details, [here](#).

Online attendees, stay in touch. The link for the online connection will be sent in the next few days.

The Mayoress of Sant Cugat, at the NEANIAS Open Event

The NEANIAS team is very proud to announce the participation of the Il·lma. Sra. Mireia Ingla, Mayoress of Sant Cugat del Vallès, at the NEANIAS event, accompanied by members of her management team (Economic Promotion, Employment, Business, Training and Commerce).

Likewise, representatives of the strategy and innovation areas of the Government of Catalonia will share their views on the opportunities that digital solutions can offer for the development of the information society and for the definition of innovative and efficient policies.

We will also meet with international representatives of the EU's innovation programmes to learn more about the European strategy and the EU's role in research.

Also, all our acknowledgment to the companies that participate, giving a market vision and presenting their success stories.

Thank you all very much for your support.

[Discover more about the agenda.](#)

NEANIAS solutions and testimonials from the industry

Many companies are supporting the NEANIAS project by using its novel IT services, already

Fig. 12 NEANIAS Open Event in the project newsletter (sample)

In addition, the mailing lists allowed the organizers to keep those registered up to date with the latest news.

The NEANIAS Open Event will be soon, next Sept 22 and 23!

A free open event to present the results of the NEANIAS project, exploit the potential of its novel technological solutions and interconnect innovation, business, and the public sector. It will take place in Sant Cugat - Barcelona, on September 22 and 23, 2022.

The event is aimed at researchers, scientists, entrepreneurs, innovators, companies, investors, business developers, consultants, disseminators, public managers, and general public interested in Space, Underwater, Atmosphere and novel Information Technologies.

Find out everything at [NEANIAS Open Event](#).

NEANIAS OPEN Event: This is the link to attend online

The event will take place in a hybrid way, in face-to-face and online format. For those who will be attending the event remotely, here is the link.

<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/89071255991>

It will be available minutes before the start of the event.

This is NEANIAS team

Fig. 13 NEANIAS mailing for Open Event (sample)

2.6.4. Communication resources

The organization of the Open Event created a set of templates, invitation letters and mailings to be sent to the target audience, considering both anonymous profiles and identified people, by all the project partners. The text could be personalized and translated into national languages if required.

2.6.5. Testimonials

Many companies supported the NEANIAS project by using its novel IT services, already available in the European Open Science Cloud. Likewise, they offer valuable collaboration through very important feedback that facilitates the implementation of features according to the needs of the market and research.

Some video testimonials from the industry, endorsing the NEANIAS Project and the Open Event, were produced. All of them are available on NEANIAS website (<https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/the-project/testimonials>) and in the NEANIAS YouTube channel.

2.6.5.1. Walldone and NEANIAS services.

Walldone is working with NEANIAS project and the services provided in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and supports the NEANIAS Open Event. Walldone (<https://walldone.gr/>) is a company aimed at co-creating flexible pathways to strengthen urban resilience and improve the quality of life in urban areas.

In this short video, Panagiotis Kolliopoulos, Walldone's Managing Director, introduces the company and presents how the NEANIAS services are helping them in their goals.

Fig. 14 Walldone endorsing NEANIAS Open Event

2.6.5.2. DDQ Pocket Science and NEANIAS services.

DDQ Pocket Science is working with NEANIAS project and the services provided in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and endorses the NEANIAS Open Event. DDQ Pocket Science (<https://www.ddq.nl/index.html>) creates and delivers innovative products and services for mobile platforms.

In this short video, Norbert Schmidt, Owner DDQ B.V. introduces the company and presents how the NEANIAS services are helping them in their goals.

Fig. 15 DDQ endorsing NEANIAS Open Event

2.6.5.3. Relief Applications and NEANIAS.

Relief applications is working with the NEANIAS project and the services provided in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and supports the NEANIAS Open Event.

Relief applications (<https://reliefapplications.org/>) is a company with the mission of bringing Innovation to People Changing the World. They design simple yet efficient IT solutions aimed at increasing the impact of humanitarian assistance and contribute to alleviate human suffering in times of crisis.

In this short video, Julio Monleon, Marketing Officer at Relief Applications, introduces the company and presents how the NEANIAS services are helping them in their goals.

Fig. 16 Relief Applications endorsing NEANIAS Open Event

2.6.5.4. GEOInsight and NEANIAS services.

GEOInsight is working with NEANIAS project and the services provided in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and endorses the NEANIAS Open Event.

GEOInsight (<https://www.geoinsight.hu/>) is a start-up business formed to commercially utilise a set of software and procedural solutions (the “GEOInsight Solution”), originally developed

at the Research Centre for Astronomy and Earth Sciences of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, specifically to support the analysis of population distributions on the basis of cellular data generated by mobile telephone system operators.

In this short video presentation, the founder and CEO of GEOInsight introduces the company and presents how the NEANIAS services are helping them in their goals.

Fig. 17 GEOInsight endorsing NEANIAS Open Event

2.6.6. Media

The event was presented in media and digital platforms. Following, some examples.

NEANIAS project and the Open Event to present the project results and services is presented at Veda a Technika (science and technology). The article is written in Slovak.

CIP > Domov > Veda a technika v EÚ > Novinky

NEANIAS Open Event

19. 9. 2022 Podujatie NEANIAS sa bude konať 22 – 23. septembra 2022.

Podujatie je zameraného na prezentáciu výsledkov projektu NEANIAS, o využití potenciálu nových technologických riešení, prepojenia inovácií, podnikov a verejného sektora. Určené je pre výskumníkov, vedcov, podnikateľov, inovátorov, spoločností, investorov, konzultantov, verejných manažérov.

Fig. 18 NEANIAS Open Event at Veda a Technika.

NEANIAS project is presented in SmartCatalonia. The text introduces the project, its objectives, the challenges and the services in the EOSC, and announces the NEANIAS Open Event. The article is written in Catalan.

The screenshot shows a webpage titled "NEANIAS Open Event". It includes social media sharing icons (Twitter, Facebook, Telegram, WhatsApp, and Print) and a "Torna" button. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column contains the word "Quan" followed by the date "Data 22.09.2022 - 22.09.2022" and time "Hora De 9.30 a 17.30 h.", with a link to "Afegeix al calendari de Google". The right column features a central image of the event banner, which reads "NEANIAS Open Event September 22-23, 2022, Sant Cugat del Vallès - Barcelona & online". To the right of the image, there is a description in Catalan: "Un esdeveniment obert i gratuït per presentar els resultats del projecte NEANIAS, explotar el potencial de les seves noves solucions tecnològiques i interconnectar innovació, empresa i sector públic." Below this is a "Programa" section listing "Dia 1 (22 de setembre de 2022)" and "SESSIÓ 1: Resultats del projecte i el núvol europeu de ciència oberta".

Fig. 19 NEANIAS Open Event presented in SmartCatalonia.

The NEANIAS free open event to present the results of the NEANIAS project, exploit the potential of its novel technological solutions and interconnect innovation, business, and the public sector. The text is written in Greek.

The screenshot shows a Greek-language announcement for the "NEANIAS Open event (Online, Spain)" on "22-23/09/2022". The author is listed as "ΣΥΓΓΡΑΦΕΑΣ: STGEORG" and the date as "ΗΜΕΡΟΜΗΝΙΑ: ΣΕΠ 19, 2022 12:08". The main text states: "After almost 3 years of continuous work the NEANIAS project is approaching its completion. Thus, the NEANIAS consortium is organizing an Open Event in Barcelona, on September 22 and 23, 2022 to present the results of the project, exploiting the potential of its innovative technological solutions and interconnect innovation, business, and the public sector." A separate box on the right specifies the date in Greek: "Καταληκτική Ημερομηνία: Τετάρτη, 21 Σεπτέμβριος, 2022". At the bottom, it lists the target audience: "The event is aimed at researchers, scientists, entrepreneurs, innovators, companies, investors, business developers, consultants, disseminators, public managers, and general public interested in".

Fig. 20 NEANIAS and its Open Event presented at DTUH.gr

NEANIAS Open Event is presented at ESADE Newsletter as a free and open event organized with the aim of presenting the results of the NEANIAS project, exploiting the potential of its innovative technological solutions and interconnecting innovation, companies and the public sector. The article is written in Spanish.

NEANIAS Open Event

- **Fecha:** Del 22/09/2022 al 23/09/2022
- **Hora:** De 9:30h a 13:30h
- **Lugar:** Auditorio Esade Creapolis o *streaming*

Los días 22 y 23 de septiembre Esade Creapolis acogerá el evento abierto y gratuito "NEANIAS Open Event", organizado con el objetivo de presentar los resultados del proyecto NEANIAS, explotar el potencial de sus **novedosas soluciones tecnológicas** e interconectar la **innovación, las empresas y el sector público**. El acto se realizará **en inglés**.

[Inscripciones](#)

Fig. 21 NEANIAS Open Event presented in ESADE Newsletter

NEANIAS project is presented in OpenAire. The text introduces the project, its objectives, the challenges and the services in the EOSC, and announces the NEANIAS Open Event.

The screenshot shows the OpenAire website interface. At the top left is the OpenAire logo. Navigation links include "Services", "Support", "Open Science In Europe", and "About". A search icon is also present. Below the navigation is a filter bar with options: "By Year", "By Month", "By Week", "Today", "Jump to month", and "By Categories". The main content area displays the event title "NEANIAS OPEN EVENT" in large blue letters, followed by a calendar icon and the dates "22 SEP 2022 - 23 SEP 2022". A short description below reads: "A free open event to present the results of the NEANIAS project, exploit the potential of its novel technological solutions and interconnect innovation, business, and the public sector."

Fig. 22 NEANIAS Open Event at OpenAire

The NEANIAS Open Event as also promoted by other research centres and H2020 projects with which NEANIAS is collaborating and exploiting synergies. Following, some examples.

The NEANIAS Open Event promoted by the University of Milano Bicocca:

The screenshot shows the website of the Dipartimento di Informatica, Sistemistica e Comunicazione DISCO at the University of Milano Bicocca. The page features the university logo, navigation links (HOME, IL DIPARTIMENTO, DIDATTICA, RICERCA, QUALITÀ, ORIENTAMENTO, INTERNATIONAL MOBILITY), and a search bar. The main content area is titled "Evento aperto progetto NEANIAS" and includes the dates "da 22 settembre 2022 a 23 settembre 2022". A brief description of the event is provided, along with a registration link: <https://www.neanias.eu/index.php/open-event/neanias-open-event>.

Fig. 23 NEANIAS Open Event presented by University Milano Bicocca

The NEANIAS Open Event promoted by the Blue-Cloud Project:

The screenshot shows the website of the Blue-Cloud Project. The page features a search bar, a navigation menu (ABOUT, SERVICES, VLABS, SUPPORT CENTRE, ROADMAP, SYNERGIES, EVENTS, MEDIA), and a "LOG IN" button. The main content area is titled "NEANIAS Open Event" and includes the date "September 22-23, 2022" and the location "Sant Cugat del Vallès - Barcelona & online". The page also features a "2 MIN READ" indicator and a large image of the NEANIAS logo and event details.

Fig. 24 NEANIAS Open Event presented by Blue Cloud Project

The NEANIAS Open Event promoted by the Green Project Expo:

The screenshot shows the NEANIAS Open Event page on the Green Project Expo website. The page has a green header with the logo and navigation elements. The main content area is a green card with a white box on the left containing a thumbnail image of the event. To the right of the thumbnail, the event details are listed: Event name: NEANIAS Open Event, Organized by: NEANIAS, Start date: September 22nd 2022, 10:00 am, Status event: public. Below the details is a 'Join the meeting' button and social sharing buttons for Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, and Instagram.

Fig. 25 NEANIAS Open Event presented by Green Project Expo

2.6.7. Meetings

Last, but not least, many meetings were held with the scientific community, researchers, innovation hubs, policymakers and public representatives, managers of public services, investors, businesspeople, companies, business hubs, start-ups, academia, media, H2020 projects and European representatives, among others, to present, explain, raise interest and engage them and invite them to attend or participate in the NEANIAS Open Event.

2.7. Registration form

The attendance to the Open Event was managed using a standard registration form. In this form the audience had to provide their contact information (mandatory) as well as optional data for follow up purposes. The form can be found [here](#).

The following figure shows the landing page with all the visuals for illustrative purposes:

A screenshot of a registration form for the NEANIAS Open Event. The top section features a banner image of a large audience in a hall, with the NEANIAS logo and the text "OPEN EVENT" overlaid. Below the banner, the form has a white background with a blue border. It includes a title "NEANIAS OPEN EVENT", a welcome message, an invitation to a free event, event details (date and location), a link to the website, a "Correo*" label, a "Correo válido" input field, and a "Cambiar configuración" link.

NEANIAS OPEN EVENT

Welcome to the NEANIAS Open Event registration form.

NEANIAS team is pleased to invite you to a free open event to present the results of the NEANIAS project, exploit the potential of its novel technological solutions, and interconnect innovation, business and the public sector.

- Date: September 22-23, 2022.
- Location: The event will take place online and in person (Esade Creapolis Innovation Hub, Av. De la Torre Blanca, 57 - 08172 Sant Cugat del Vallès, Barcelona, Spain).

All the details at <https://www.neanias.eu/>

Correo *

Correo válido

Este formulario registra los correos. [Cambiar configuración](#)

Fig. 26 Registration form (sample)

3. Development of the Open Event

This section reports about the development of the event, including all the details about the content, the presenters and the venue.

3.1. Content

3.1.1. Agenda

The agenda was structured in 3 sessions allocated in 2 days. The leaders of each presentation are also specified.

Day 1, Session 1: Project results and the European Open Science Cloud.

A presentation on the NEANIAS project, the European innovation strategies, the European Open Science Cloud and the new opportunities for business, research, and public management.

9:30 Arrival and welcome

10:00 Digital innovation for public management, business and research

- Il·lma. Sra. Mireia Ingla. Mayoress of Sant Cugat del Vallès
- Paul D. Williams. University of Reading, UK, EU Representative
- Eduard Falcó, Government of Catalunya
- Mema Roussopoulos, NEANIAS Project Coordinator

10:20 NEANIAS and the goals and strategic challenges in Europe

- Mema Roussopoulos, Project Coordinator
- Eleni Petra, Project Manager
- Daniel Martinez, Dissemination WP leader

10:45 NEANIAS in the EOSC strategy

- George Papastefanatos, EOSC WP leader

10:55 Coffee break – networking

11:15 Space digital services overview

- Eva Sciacca, Space WP leader

11:30 Atmosphere digital services overview

- Nikos Chondros, Atmosphere WP manager

11:45 Underwater digital services overview

- Evi Nomikou, Underwater WP leader

12:00 Enabling and delivering innovative services in NEANIAS

- Giorgos Papanikos, Delivery WP leader

12:15 Business perspective of NEANIAS solutions

- Ioannis Neokosmidis, Assessment WP leader

12:30 European Innovation Strategy and NEANIAS contributions

- Konstantinos Karantzalos, Scientific coordinator

12:45 Open questions and Conclusions

- Eleni Petra, NEANIAS Project Manager
- Eduard Falcó Government of Catalonia
- Ignasi Bonet, Government of Catalonia
- NEANIAS Project Management Board

13:00 End of session 1**Lunch – Networking****Day 1, Session 2: Innovation and business session**

Participative innovation and business workshops led by our innovation specialists and business consultants. Learn about the success cases and the experiences of on-boarded users and companies and discover more about their results and the benefits achieved with the NEANIAS solutions in the European Open Science Cloud.

14:00 NEANIAS Innovation activities and the results of the open innovation workshops

- Katalin Kovács, supported by thematic experts

14:20 Business Cases

- Katalin Kovács, supported by business cases representatives

15:50 Coffee break - networking**16:15 Open discussion: Further business/technical opportunities and possible ways of collaboration**

- Katalin Kovács, business cases representatives, thematic experts

17:05 Questions from the audience

- NEANIAS Project Board

17:30. End of session 2**Day 2 Session 3: Technical session**

Find out all about the innovative NEANIAS services available at EOSC from our experts and developers. Learn to make the most of its potential and apply it effectively to meet the needs of your projects or your research. In addition to the thematic presentations, NEANIAS consultants, researchers and developers was at the audience's disposal throughout the morning to comment on anything they need and find the best way to support their lines of research or enhance your solutions.

9:30 Space services technical presentations. Interactive presentations and demos

- Eva Sciacca & service leaders

10:20 Coffee break - networking**10:30 Atmosphere services technical presentations. Interactive presentations and demos**

- Nikos Chondros & service leaders

11:20 Coffee break - networking**11:30 Underwater services technical presentations. Interactive presentations and demos**

- Evi Nomikou & service leaders
- 12:20 Coffee break - networking
- 12:30 Core services technical presentations. Interactive presentations and demos
- Attila Farkas & service leaders
- 13:20 Conclusions and closing
- Mema Roussopoulos
 - Eleni Petra
 - Daniel Martinez
- 13:30 Networking and end of the day
- All the NEANIAS team

All sessions were very participatory, allowing and encouraging the participation of face-to-face or remote attendees.

3.1.2. Demonstrations

The NEANIAS services were presented, explained and tested by the audience. In addition, additional demonstrations were available from the NEANIAS technical team and developers during the two days of the event in a dedicated hall. This allowed, in a more personalized way, to answer all the specific questions from the audience during networking breaks or at scheduled times.

3.1.3. Networking

Throughout the event numerous breaks were scheduled to facilitate networking between the NEANIAS team and the attending public, both in person and online, on any topic related to the functionality of the services, performance, technical or operational issues, the EOSC framework, the commercial framework and commercial aspects, the exploitation aspects or even the possible collaboration in future actions.

The feedback obtained let us know that the initiative was very fruitful.

3.2. Presenters

In addition to the members of the project, the event included the participation of invited personalities of recognized renown in science, politics or innovation that facilitated the promotion and attraction of attendees.

The Open Event presenters are introduced below.

3.2.1. Guest presenters

Mireia Ingla

Mireia Ingla i Mas, Mayoress of Sant Cugat del Vallès. Graduated in Law through the University of Barcelona, she also has a postgraduate degree in Family Mediation and is specialized in Housing Law and Family Law. She has collaborated with Caritas and its Housing Mediation Service, and during her youth she worked in a law firm specialized in the defence of human rights, with which travelled to Geneva and the United Nations.

Eduard Falcó

Eduard Falcó, MSc in Telecommunications Engineering, is strategic consultant at the Catalan Government, working in the development of the information society in Catalonia, the digitalization of the Administration, the digital transformation of the country, and managing innovative projects in digital area. In different EU projects has worked in many different areas (FP7, 8 and 9). He has been facing with rollout projects of optical fibre and 5G or AI and Living Labs projects, trying to bring innovation throughout the territory and not just of metropolitan areas. He has also collaborated with Cooperation and Development Agency of Catalan Government to introduce the digital component in their programs (Tunisia, Mozambique, Senegal, others.).

J. Ignasi Bonet

J. Ignasi Bonet is a Digital Innovation Manager at CTTI, public company from the Government of Catalunya. From a global education and eclectic interests, he is a connector, a social linker who put in contact challenges with solutions, supply with demand, in a creative and innovative way. He began his career as a technical sales support for a Global Operator, strategic consultant and project manager for public administration. Former Director of Innovation at Sant Cugat City Hall nowadays is in the Digital Innovation Department of the provider of digital solutions of the Government of Catalunya.

Paul D. Williams

Dr. Paul Williams is Professor of Atmospheric Science at the University of Reading, UK, and member of NEANIAS External Advisory Board. Educated in physics to PhD level at Oxford, he specialises in meteorology, with a focus on weather-sensitive applications including aviation. He has published two books and over 60 scientific papers in leading journals, including Nature. He is a consultant to Guinness World Records on extreme atmospheric events. He is also an award-winning science communicator, regularly giving public lectures and appearing in media.

3.2.2. NEANIAS Team

Mema Dimitra-Isidora Roussopoulou

Mema Dimitra-Isidora Roussopoulou is an Associate Professor of Computer Science and head of the Distributed Systems Research Group in the Department of Informatics and Telecommunications at the University of Athens. She received her PhD in Computer Science from Stanford University. She was an Assistant Professor of Computer Science on the Gordon McKay Endowment at Harvard University. She was also a faculty member at the Department of Computer Science at the University of Crete and an Associated Researcher at the Institute of Computer Science at FORTH, where she headed the Large-Scale Peer-to-Peer Systems Group. Her interests are in the areas of distributed systems, networking, mobile computing, and digital preservation. Her work has been published in prestigious conferences and journals in computer systems and networking. She served as Chair of the Working Group on Privacy and Technology of ENISA, the European Network and Information Security Agency in 2007-2008. She has several years of experience managing and working on projects at the national and European level as well as in the US. She is currently Associate Editor of IEEE Transactions in Cloud Computing. Finally, she is a recipient of the NSF CAREER award from the National Science Foundation, the ERC Starting Grant Award from the European Research Council, and the Best Paper Award at ACM SOSP 2003.

Eleni Petra

Eleni Petra holds a Diploma in Computer Engineering and Informatics, Technical University of Patras, Greece, and a Master of Science in Computation, University of Manchester, Institute of Science and Technology. Over the past 32 years she is working as a Scientific consultant and Project Manager for a number of Research Centres, companies, government agencies, and the EU. She has served as a Project Manager and Technical Coordinator for the technical and management support and consulting of 6.800 ICT development projects for Greece in the framework of the Sectoral Operational Programme “Information Society” of the National Strategic Reference Framework (NSRF) as Deloitte senior manager, as Project Manager and Technical Coordinator of over 65 industrial areas development projects of PIRAEUS BANK and ETVA, as Project Manager and Technical Coordinator for the MIS in the Greek Ministries of Public Works and Industry. Currently, she is working at NKUA and ATHENA RC as Project Manager in Horizon2020 projects related to research infrastructures, Cloud Infrastructure projects for fisheries, marine and aquaculture domains, cutting - edge research infrastructures for medicine and Greek Infrastructures for research and culture.

Daniel Martinez Sala

Daniel Martinez Sala is a Business and Innovation Consulting Manager at RICOH Digital Services. He holds a degree in engineering in Electronics from Ramon Llull University (Barcelona) and a degree in Telecommunications (Barcelona). He also has an MBA from LaSalle Business Engineering School (Barcelona & San Francisco, California). He is an experienced consulting manager and team leader in strategic and business consultancy as well as in technological innovation in the information and communication technologies field, working in the development of the information society and the digital transformation. He has worked on many innovation projects, both in the private and public sector, including innovation programmes of the European Union. He complements his experience through the collaboration in publications of a scientific / informative nature and teaching, being a professor at Ramon Llull University since 1999.

George Papastefanatos

Dr. George Papastefanatos is a principal researcher at Athena Research Center. He holds a Diploma in Electrical and Computer Engineering and PhD in Computer Science from the National Technical University of Athens. George has more than 20 years of active involvement as a researcher and technical and project manager in several RTD projects, including projects related to Big Data engineering, big data visualization and analytics and the European Open Science Cloud activities. George participates as a technical manager and researcher in a series of research projects which are developing EOSC (he is the product owner of the EOSC Service catalogue in EOSC Future, EOSC-ENHANCE, and eInfraCentral projects which develop component in the EOSC Portal, CatRIS, which builds the catalogue of services of Research Infrastructures and NEANIAS). George's expertise is in the areas of big data management, data services on the cloud and data analytics and specifically in issues related to data integration information visualization and visual analytics. He has co-authored more than 80 papers in these areas, 1 book and 3 chapters in books, and 3 of his articles have been awarded best paper prizes in conferences.

Eva Sciacca

Eva Sciacca is an Information Technology researcher at the Istituto Nazionale di Astrofisica (INAF). Her recent research activities are related to: big-data and visual analytic, computing and data systems exploiting Cloud and HPC infrastructures. She has been engaged in the last 5 years in several European funded projects (such as VIALACTEA, INDIGO-Data Cloud, AENEAS, EOSC-Pilot) and she is actually leader of the SPACE Research Services WP of the H2020 NEANIAS Project. She is actively involved within the IT activities of the Square Kilometre Array (SKA) and their precursors/pathfinders.

Nikos Chondros

Nikos Chondros is a Senior Researcher and Software Engineer working the Distributed Systems Group at the Department of Informatics & Telecommunications at the University of Athens. He received his Master's and PhD degrees from the University of Athens. He has founded and run his own software development and IT consulting company and has over twenty years of experience in leading and managing projects involved in the analysis, design, development, deployment, and maintenance of information systems for several major companies including Citibank NY, Citibank London, IKEA, Vodafone, IBM, and several banks in the Middle East. He also has several years of experience working in research and development projects at the national and European level.

Paraskevi Nomikou

Paraskevi Nomikou received a PhD from UoA in 2004 and has participated in more than 80 oceanographic cruises that have focused on the study of submarine volcanism, mud volcanoes, landslides and slope stability and the exploration of seafloor mineral deposits in Med Sea, Atlantic and Pacific Ocean. She has developed a unique understanding of the new-technological methods for deep-sea exploration and successfully integrated them into international research programs. More recently, she has played a leading role in the evaluation of the potential hazards associated with renewed volcanic activity at Santorini volcano in Greece in 2011. Her studies of the underwater area of the volcano where new earthquakes and deformation have been taking place are critical to the on-going evaluation of future eruption scenarios. She has been a keyperson for both local civil officials and the general population to understand the geological processes that might occur and what would be appropriate. She has also been involved in the study of economically important seafloor mineral deposits within the crater of the submarine volcano Kolumbo, off the coast of Santorini. Paraskevi is focused in forming key research alliances between scientists in different disciplines thus creating powerful interdisciplinary synergies.

Georgios Papanikos

Georgios Papanikos, is a senior software engineer with long experience in distributed processing, data and metadata management, visualization, Service Oriented Architectures, security etc. He has been engaged in several infrastructure projects and has long experience with geospatial data management and visualization approaches as well as platforms such as condor HPC, Hadoop, Apache Spark etc. He is also a backend developer quite experienced in well-known stacks of major ecosystems.

Ioannis Neokosmidis

Dr. Ioannis Neokosmidis is the CEO of Incites Consulting SARL. He holds a Physics degree, a M.Sc. in Radioelectrology and Electronics and Ph.D diploma in optical nonlinear networks from

the University of Athens. He has more than 15 years of experience working with operators, regulators and enterprises across Europe. His primary areas of specialisation include consulting on investment and strategy decision making in the telecoms sector. He has considerable expertise in the areas of next-generation access networks (NGAN) and both fixed and mobile termination rates having participated in respective projects assigned by the Greek NRA. Dr. Neokosmidis has also worked on business planning and market assessment projects. He has more than 35 publications with two best paper awards and more than 250 citations. His research interests include System of Systems, Deep Uncertainties, Advanced forecasting techniques and Technoeconomics. He serves as reviewer in leading IEEE/OSA Journals and conferences.

Konstantinos Karantzalos

Konstantinos Karantzalos received his engineering diploma from the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA, Greece) and his PhD (2007, NTUA) in collaboration with Ecole Nationale de Ponts et Chaussees (ENPC, France). In 2007, he joined the Department of Applied Mathematics at Ecole Centrale de Paris (ECP, France) as a postdoc. He is currently an Associate Professor of Remote Sensing at the National Technical University of Athens. His teaching and research interests include geoscience and remote sensing, big data, hyperspectral image analysis, computer vision and pattern recognition, environmental monitoring and precision agriculture. Several of his publications have been featured in top-ranking international journals and conferences. He has more than 19 years of research experience and has been involved with more than 28 EU and national excellence/ competitive research projects. He is the Scientific Coordinator of NEANIAS EU project.

Katalin Kovács

Katalin Kovács, senior consultant at innomine. She has 10 years of experience in the field of international innovation and project development both from industry, university and innovation agencies. She has a PhD degree from the Budapest University of Technology and Economics, research area is innovation management, specialization is living labs. During her professional work, she started to work at the Central Hungarian Innovation Agency and focused on EU financed innovation project management. Later on she worked for the Zoltan Bay research institute (major research institute in Hungary) with a specialization of international EU funded projects. Before joining innomine she worked in Graz for the European Sustainable Energy Innovation Alliance. Currently she is senior consultant at innomine. She is author of 10+ articles and is an experienced speaker at international conferences.

Attila Farkas

Attila Farkas is a research associate at the Laboratory of Parallel and Distributed Systems (LPDS) at the Institute for Computer Science and Control (SZTAKI), Eötvös Loránd Research Network (ELKH). He received his Computer Science Engineering BSc and MSc degrees from the Óbuda University, John von Neumann Faculty of Informatics. Since 2020, he has been pursuing his PhD research on the topic of distributed deep learning. He has been involved in COLA and NEANIAS European H2020 projects. His research interests focus on parallel computing, clouds, container technologies and machine learning.

Simone Mantovani

Mantovani Simone (MSc Physics) M, mantovani@meeo.it – senior project manager – has more than 18 of experience in EO system developments and implementation in the framework of ESA, FP7, H2020 projects. Simone is the team leader of the technical team responsible of all the implementations of ADAM platform.

Robert Lovas

Dr. Robert Lovas is the deputy head of the Laboratory of the Parallel and Distributed Systems at the Institute for Computer Science and Control, Hungarian Academy of Sciences (MTA SZTAKI). He received his MSc degree in Electrical Engineering and PhD degree in Informatics from the Budapest University of Technology and Economics, and currently acts as a habilitated associate professor at the John von Neumann Faculty of Informatics, Óbuda University. His solid experience in wide range of research and development fields of computational chemistry, numerical meteorological modeling, bioinformatics, precision agriculture, connected Cars, and Industry 4.0 has been gained in various global, European and national ICT collaborations with academic organizations, universities, and enterprises. He coordinated two e-infrastructure projects in the EU 7th Framework Programme to build and integrate computing services for research communities. More than 75 scientific papers and book chapters on software engineering for Grid, Cloud, Big Data computing platforms particularly from workflow-oriented design, orchestration, debugging, and application aspects are included in his publication records.

Rafael Garcia

Rafael Garcia, PhD in Computer Engineering. His research activity is mainly focused on underwater robotics in topics such as large-scale seafloor mapping, sensor fusion, 3D reconstruction and semantic representation of video imagery. He provides support in the research activities of the company and is the director of the Underwater Vision Lab of the University of Girona. He has been visiting researcher at the Universität der Bundeswehr (Germany), University College Cork (Ireland), IRISA-INRIA (France), and the University of Miami (USA). Dr. Garcia has published three books, 47 JCR journals and more than 100 papers in peer review international conferences and he has directed 9 PhDs thesis.

Ricardo Vitorino

Ricardo Vitorino is the Smart Cities R&I Manager at Ubiwhere. Ricardo holds an MSc. Degree in Computer Science from the University of Coimbra, having started working in 2011, in the Smart Cities and Mobility area, where he helped creating an open-data platform for urban mobility called One.Stop.Transport (OST). Since then, he has worked on projects related to the smart cities context and had some experience with FIWARE technology, mainly in the FIWARE Lisbon pilot, where he helped publishing data from OST into CKAN, FIWARE's open data portal. He joined Ubiwhere in early 2015 to work on its Smart Cities solutions (Citibrain), mainly the backend services (REST APIs) regarding mobility. Ricardo is currently responsible for the technical team working on Smart Cities software solutions.

Georgios Kakalettris

Georgios Kakalettris, MSc is a senior software architect, CTO of CITE, with more than 20 years of experience in commercial and research projects with roles that spanned from software engineer and researcher to workpackage and technical leader. Since early 2000 he has been engaged in Geospatial data management and visualization and distributed processing and

metadata federation / information retrieval and several large-scale applications for various sectors such as finance, human resource management, infrastructure management, culture etc

Giuseppe Vizzari

Giuseppe Vizzari has been working on analysis, modelling and simulation of complex systems, employing approaches from Artificial Intelligence, for over 15 years. He published more than 120 papers on international journals and conferences (H-index: 20 – Google Scholar, 14 – Scopus). He has participated several Italian and international research projects (most of them of interdisciplinary nature, for instance in collaboration with researchers from civil engineering, urban planning, psychology, cultural heritage), in addition to some collaborations with industrial partners.

Angelo Pio Rossi

Angelo Pio Rossi, geologist by background, is professor of Earth and Planetary Science at Jacobs University. He has been involved in several planetary mapping and data exploitation activities, in addition to various scientific coordination roles (e.g., 2009 ASI/USGS geological mapping workshop). He is lead for the Planetary Service (<http://planetserver.eu>) as well as coordinator of the H2020 EarthServer project. He is deputy coordinator of the EuroPlanet VESPA activity (<http://europlanet-vespa.eu/>). And H2020 Space Planmap (<http://planmap.eu>) He has organized major sessions, workshops and conferences, as well as edited a variety of journal special issues and books, and he is associate editor of Planetary and Space Science. He co-founded the OpenPlanetary initiative (<http://openplaneatry.org>) and he serves as editor-in-chief of Planetary and Space Science.

Paul Wintersteller

Paul Wintersteller, M.Sc. Geology, is a senior research associate at Teledyne. While he focused on the analysis of remote sensing data during his studies, he gained his experiences and skills in hydrography when participating on more than 70 expedition cruises within the last 18 years, mainly with focus to hydrographic support. Within the last years he led the quality management of the INTERREG IV project “Tiefenschärfe – High resolution mapping of Lake Constance” and participates the EU funded EMODNet Bathymetry project as well as the Helmholtz Initiative and Networking Fund Project “MaNIDA - Marine Network for Integrated Data Access”. His scientific interests lie in habitat mapping, high-resolution AUV-born bathymetry and investigations around cold seeps, mud volcanos and cold-water corals.

3.3. Venue

This section shows some operational, organizational and technical details that facilitated the development of the NEANIAS Open Event.

3.3.1. Conference room

The conference room was the place where the presentations took place. Next, some illustrative images.

D10.5 NEANIAS open event

Fig. 27 NEANIAS Open Event conference room.

Fig. 28 NEANIAS Project Management Board and invited personalities on the stage

3.3.2. Lobby and demonstrations area

Next, some illustrative pictures on the demonstration area.

D10.5 NEANIAS open event

Fig. 29 NEANIAS Open Event. Demo area (sample)

Fig. 30 NEANIAS Open Event. Demo area (sample 2)

3.3.3. Networking area

This area was dedicated to facilitating the networking. Next figure illustrates an online meeting between panelists and online attendees during a break.

Fig. 31 NEANIAS Open Event. Networking area

Next, networking during the lunch.

Fig. 32 NEANIAS Open Event. Networking area during coffee break

3.3.4. Visuals and promotional material

The organization of the event included the design, production and installation of physical elements, such as signage, posters, brochures and promotional material.

Some examples are shown in next figures:

Fig. 33 NEANIAS Open Event. Roll-up

D10.5 NEANIAS open event

Fig. 34 NEANIAS Open Event. Brochures

Fig. 35 NEANIAS Open Event. Signage

D10.5 NEANIAS open event

Fig. 36 NEANIAS Open Event. Stage details, including banners, screens, video projector and others

Fig. 37 NEANIAS Open Event. Multimedia equipment in the lobby, with demonstration videos and project information

3.3.5. IT and communication team

The NEANIAS Open Event took place in a hybrid way, face-to-face and online.

Fig. 38 NEANIAS Open Event. IT team, managing the Zoom platform

Fig. 39 NEANIAS Open Event. IT team, managing the Zoom platform (2)

3.3.6. Assistants

Also, mention that there was an organization team that facilitated the processes of welcome and control of attendees, as well as support for the proper development of the event.

4. Results and Impact

4.1. Audience overview

The event aroused interest among stakeholders, which resulted in 147 people participating in the different activities of the event. Below is a brief breakdown of the audience, complying with the GDPR commitments.

Considering the sessions that made up the NEANIAS Open Event, the one that aroused the greatest interest was the first one, “NEANIAS results and the European Open Science Cloud”. Being much more transversal and general, it was of interest to a much broader audience while also serving as an introduction to the subsequent ones. The second session, “Innovation and business session”, was aimed mainly at companies, business representatives and end users, and the third one “Technical session” was aimed at technicians, service managers, integrators, specialists and final users of the NEANIAS solutions.

Fig. 40 Attendees by session

The main fields of interest were the Innovative IT services and solutions, and innovation and open science. Government and public management solutions and the business investment opportunities were the second group of interest- A third group is composed by the thematic solutions in the NEANIAS fields (underwater, atmospheric and space), much less transversal than the previous ones and with a much more specific target. Categorized as Others, complementary interests or additional topics identified by the audience are included such as agriculture, social progress or data science.

Fig. 41 Attendees by field of interest

The profile of the attendees gave the organizers preliminary information on the approach and the technical level of the sessions to be planned, identifying the most suitable presenters for each one, mainly in the interactive and networking sessions. All the target profiles of the project were represented in the event.

Fig. 42 Attendees by position

Regarding the type of organization, the most represented were research institutes and universities, followed by business (SME and large companies), public administrations and start-ups.

Fig. 43 Attendees by type of organization

The event took place in Sant Cugat del Vallès, Barcelona (Spain), where the NEANIAS team was present, giving attendees the opportunity to attend in person. Furthermore, the event was also offered online, giving the audience an additional opportunity to attend while avoiding scheduling constraints, unforeseen expenses, or health concerns. It was also a good opportunity to open the event internationally.

Fig. 44 Attendees by type of participation

61% of the audience participated virtually.

As for the origin of those attending the event, about half came from Spain, the country where the event took place.

Attendees by country

Fig. 45 Attendees by country

The next figure provides a deeper view about the event worldwide.

Attendees by country (worldwide)

Fig. 46 Attendees by country (worldwide)

Finally, as an additional element of analysis, the gender of the participants was asked solely for statistical purposes. This field was not mandatory, and people had the right to refuse to answer.

Fig. 47 Attendees by gender

67% of the responses were men and 28% women.

4.2. Indirect impact

The participation of relevant personalities in the NEANIAS Open Event facilitated the dissemination of the NEANIAS project and its solutions to third parties, belonging to the world of politics, research and business. It is especially worth highlighting the promotion and networking capacity of the following people:

- Ilma. Ms. Mireia Ingla, Mayoress of Sant Cugat del Vallès, as well as the members of her team accompanying her.
- Ms. Elena Vila, deputy mayoress for Economic Promotion, Employment, Business, Training and Trade matters.
- Mr. Pere Soler deputy mayor for Presidency, Finance, Urban Services, Mobility and Security matters.
- Mr., Víctor Puntas, City Council Head of the Mayor's Office.
- Mr. Mikel Vilalta, City Council Deputy Mayor's Office.
- Ms. Anna Alvarez, City Council Director of Economic Promotion, Employment, Business, Training and Trade.
- Ms. Carme Calvo, City Council office for Economic Promotion, Employment, Business and Commerce.
- Mr. Eduard Falcó, Advisor at the Government of Catalunya.
- Mr. Ignasi Bonet, Innovation manager at the Government of Catalunya.
- Professor Paul D. Williams, from the University of Reading, UK, and member of NEANIAS External Advisory Board.
- Ms. Tünde Szabó from Geoinsight.
- Mr. Norbert Schmidt, from DDQ.
- Mr. Julio Monleon, from Relief Applications.
- Mr. Panagiotis Kolliopoulos, from Walldone.
- Mr. Angelos Tserekas Zafeirakis, from Sotiria.
- Mr. Stergios Kokorotsikos, from Eunice.
- Ms. Noela Pina, from Ubiwhere.
- Angels Baqué, from Esade.

4.3. Media impact

The NEANIAS Open Event had diffusion on media and digital channels.

NEANIAS project was presented at Cugat.Cat. The newspaper points out that the city of Sant Cugat reaffirms its commitment to the city of science and innovation with the NEANIAS project. The article is written in Catalan.

Fig. 48 Picture published in the newspaper Cugat.cat

Next, mayoress of the city interviewed by media:

Fig. 49 Mayoress interviewed by the press at the NEANIAS Open Event

Next image shows the Dissemination and Communication Manager attending the media.

Fig. 50 Communication and Dissemination manager attending the media

Next, tweet by Il·lma. Sra. Mireia Ingla, mayoress of Sant Cugat del Vallès, promoting the NEANIAS project and showing her participation in the NEANIAS Open Event.

Fig. 51 Il·lma. Mireia Ingla, Mayoress of Sant Cugat del Vallès, endorsing NEANIAS Project and the Open Event

Next figures show Dr Paul Williams, professor of Atmospheric Science at the University of Reading, UK, and member of NEANIAS External Advisory Board, endorsing and promoting his participation at the NEANIAS Open Event.

Fig. 52 Prof. Paul D. Williams and NEANIAS Open Event (sample)

Fig. 53 Fig. 46 Prof. Paul D. Williams and NEANIAS Open Event (sample)

5. Management and Coordination

The event is organized and funded by the WP10 leader, RICOH. The NEANIAS partners supported it with content, participation, presentations, demonstrations and user engagement according to their particular profiles.

All NEANIAS partners were requested to actively participate, invite and attract their partners, collaborators and contacts to the event. All project topics needed to be explained to a wide and varied audience, covering as many fields as possible, thus requiring the different skills and knowledge of all NEANIAS partners.

The beginning of the organization activities of the NEANIAS Open Event began a year before it took place. It was included as a key topic in the presentation corresponding to WP10 at the 5th General Meeting held in Catania (Sicily) on September 6, 2021.

Initially planned for June 2022 (M32), it was changed to September 2022 after an agreement with the EU to allow for more mature and consolidated services in EOSC. In addition, users already enrolled could share their experiences and success stories with the rest of the stakeholders.

The following figures show the presentation of the preliminary discussions of the Organization of the Open Event.

6. NEANIAS Open Event
Firsts steps

Expected around M32. Users on-boarding.

To be discussed:

- How?** Virtual & F2F
- When?** Suggested June 2022 (prerequisite: services / datasets ready)
- Duration?** Half a day ?
- Target audience**
 - Final users (Underwater, Atmospheric, Space).
 - EOSC community
 - European partners
- Approach?** Business / functional / technical?
- Synergies with capacity building activities
- Where?** Where is the main audience!
- Role of 3rd parties?** (other h2020, EOSC,
- Awards / acknowledgements?**

8/09/2021 NEANIAS 5TH GENERAL MEETING 20

Fig. 54 Open Event meeting at GA (1)

6. NEANIAS Open Event
Next steps

- › Identify the participants. Executive committee with representatives of all WP.
- › Agreement of road map and milestones
- › Agreement of promotion and attraction actions
- › Preliminary milestones:
 - Jan 2022: Format & firsts content agreed
 - Feb 2022: Preliminary feed-back by close potential users
 - Mar 2022: Closing and starting of promotion

8/09/2021 NEANIAS 5TH GENERAL MEETING 22

Fig. 55 Open Event meeting at GA (2)

The organization of the Open Event meant a recurrent task of internal and external engagement, presenting the objectives, discussing the strategic approach, analysing the innovation framework and the content to offer, synchronizing it with the current progress of the project and its solutions, and the feed-back of the users.

It has been coordinated from the WP10 Dissemination Committee, represented by all the WP.

NEANIAS Open Event
Goal

Open event to show and engage NEANIAS stakeholders to know, learn, appreciate, wish and endorse the NEANIAS services.
And to get feed-back from them.

30/09/2021 NEANIAS OPEN EVENT MEETING 3

Fig. 56 Open Event meeting at WP10 (sample)

The main topics were also presented and discussed in the Project Management Board meetings and General Meetings.

6. Conclusions

The NEANIAS Open Event allowed the consortium to present the objectives of the project, its motivations, the challenges assumed, the results obtained and the innovative digital solutions available on the EOSC platform, offering a complete and practical knowledge of the NEANIAS project to the world.

The event reached both to NEANIAS stakeholders and general audience. The participation of the NEANIAS partners (many of them in person) allowed us to present the full scope of the NEANIAS project (Underwater, Space, Atmospheric and Core services) from all its perspectives - strategic, functional, business, commercial, technological, innovation, user needs, EOSC and the European framework – as well as to engage potential users and to promote their onboarding.

The business and innovation session, led by NEANIAS experts and supported by companies already onboarded on NEANIAS services, presented different use and success cases and opened interesting discussions with the audience.

The technical sessions, presented by the developers of the services, gave the end users a close idea of what they can get from NEANIAS: the added value, the expected benefits and all the technology behind it. The demonstrations led by the NEANIAS technicians meant an added value for them.

The networking activities also helped the audience gain quick and fruitful access to the project team. It was carried out through multiple coffee breaks, lunch and a dedicated space in the lobby.

The NEANIAS branding was granted through the promotional material placed on the stage (banners, roll-ups) as well as all the material, brochures, posters and signage distributed in the conference room and adjacent spaces, also supported by multimedia content reproduced in a loop presenting all the NEANIAS services

The audience included policymakers, public institutions, the media, universities and research centres, managers of national IT infrastructures, business (both SMEs and large enterprises), start-ups, clusters and business organizations, and other innovative projects, among others, mainly from Europe but also from all over the world.

It is worth mentioning the active participation in person of the mayoress of the city, Ilma. Mrs. Mireia Ingla, the representatives of the Government of Catalonia, Mr. Eduard Falcó and Mr. Ignasi Bonet, as well as other public representatives and deputy mayors and managers. Likewise, our thanks to Dr. Paul Williams, professor of Atmospheric Sciences at the University of Reading and member of the External Advisory Board of NEANIAS, who also had an active face to face participation.

Annex I. Image Gallery

As annex, some illustrative pictures displaying the event development.

Fig. 57 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 58 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 59 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 60 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

D10.5 NEANIAS open event

Fig. 61 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 62 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 63 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 64 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 65 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 66 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

D10.5 NEANIAS open event

Fig. 67 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 68 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

D10.5 NEANIAS open event

Fig. 69 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 70 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

D10.5 NEANIAS open event

Fig. 71 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 72 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

D10.5 NEANIAS open event

Fig. 73 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 74 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

D10.5 NEANIAS open event

Fig. 75 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 76 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

D10.5 NEANIAS open event

Fig. 77 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 78 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

D10.5 NEANIAS open event

Fig. 79 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 80 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

D10.5 NEANIAS open event

Fig. 81 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

Fig. 82 NEANIAS Open Event development (sample)

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
OTF	Outreach task force
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
WP	Work Package
WWW	World Wide Web